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Executive summary

Sustainable space exploration requires the development of In-Situ Resource Utilization (ISRU) technologies, which encompass all processes that utilize local resources to generate useful products for robotic and human exploration. Among the available resources, water is the most versatile and most needed in space exploration. Water can be directly used as consumable for astronauts or electrolyzed to hydrogen and oxygen, a very effective rocket propellant combination. However, in-situ water extraction is challenging and the required technologies are not yet fully developed. The LUXEX project foresees the development and validation of a complete in-situ water process chain including water extraction, purification and quality monitoring. An integrated test setup will be built to validate the operational capabilities of these technologies and also of the whole process chain. This setup will deliver a relatively realistic environment analogue to the lunar surface and will use a lunar dust-ice simulant to provide proper validation conditions to raise the TRL of all subsystems and the whole process chain to level 4. The interdisciplinary nature of LUXEX combines research and innovation in space engineering, space science and exploration, geophysics and terrestrial water systems. Large space industry (Thales Alenia Space Italia), research organizations (DLR), SMEs (Liquifer Systems Group, Scanway) and academia (Technische Universität Braunschweig, Wrocław University of Science and Technology) from four European countries (Germany, Italy, Austria, Poland) join forces in a unique consortium to enable breakthroughs in ISRU technologies. LUXEX will help to strengthen the excellence in European space science and exploration and also foster the competitiveness of the European space sector.

The following is the first issue of the LUXEX system requirements and interface document (SRD). The requirements and interfaces were initially identified by analysis of the proposal submitted to the EU HORIZON-CL4-2022-SPACE-01-82 program Space Science and Exploration Technologies, "LUXEX Validation of Lunar Water Extraction and Purification Technologies for In-Situ Propellant and Consumables Production", P. Zabel et al, Proposal no. SEP-210808099. These requirements were substantially updated as a result of the Concurrent Engineering (CE) preliminary design study with the complete LUXEX team held at the DLR, Bremen, Germany, between 23-27, January, 2023. The resulting SRD still has a number of TBDs (high-lighted in yellow) that will be addressed up to the Preliminary Design Review (PDR).

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Acronyms

Acronym	Explanation	Acronym	Explanation
A	Analysis		
CE	Concurrent Engineering		
DLR	Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V.		
I	Inspection		
L-Chamber	Large-scale comet simulation Chamber		
LSG	Liquifer Systems Group GmbH		
LUXWEX	Lunar Water Extraction and Purification Technologies		
PDR	Preliminary Design Review		
ROD	Review of Design		
SW	Scanway sp. z.o. o.		
T	Test		
TBD	To be decided		
TUBS	Technische Universität Braunschweig		
TAS	Thales Alenia Space Italia		
TVAC	Thermal Vacuum Chamber		
WPS	Water Purification Subsystem		
WUST	Wroclaw University for Science and Technology		

1 System Requirements

LUWEX design requirements

1.1.1 Overall design performance

LUWEX shall implement a design that can extract purified water from 1-5 kg ice-regolith simulant with a water content of 5-20%. The product water shall fulfil the standards for both potable water and electrolysis needs.

1.1 *[Responsible: DLR/All] [Verification: ROD]*

1.1.2 LUWEX ice-regolith water extraction methodology

The LUWEX ice-regolith water extractor design shall be based on the following method:

Excavated extraction, separated functions – water extracted by heating regolith in reactor chamber using electrical heaters. Ice-regolith simulant to be prepared off-line and delivered separately to Thermal Vacuum Chamber (TVAC) extraction crucible.

[Responsible: DLR] [Verification: ROD]

1.1.3 LUWEX ambient environment

The LUWEX design shall implement a concept where water is extracted under simulated lunar polar environmental conditions as in Table 1-1.

Table 1-1 LUWEX ambient parameters compared with Moon

	Moon bulk parameter	LUWEX requirement
Polar crater cold trap	<163°C	-190C
Night-time atmospheric pressure	3 x 10 ⁻¹² mbar	< 10 ⁻⁶ mbar*
Highlands regolith mineralogy	>70% anorthosite	>70% anorthosite simulant

**Although vacuum residual pressure in LUWEX not as low as for Moon, this is still low enough for meeting LUWEX objectives*

[Responsible: TUBS, DLR] [Verification: ROD]

1.1.4 Product water purification

The LUWEX design shall incorporate a Water Purification Subsystem (PWS) within the process chain which allows for the study of the interfaces between the water extraction and the purification unit. The LUWEX WPS shall evaluate to include different treatment processes (e.g., multi-filtration, adsorbents, reverse osmosis), which are also used in state-of-the-art life support systems (ECLSS).

[Responsible: TAS, DLR] [Verification: ROD]

1.1.5 Telemetry and tele-commanding (T&TC) of LUWEX

1.2 All LUWEX sensor telemetry monitoring and tele-commanding shall be controlled via dedicated LUWEX control PC using LabVIEW application.

Note: The TVAC shall use its own dedicated T&TC for telemetry and commanding. A subset of the TVAC sensor data may be integrated with the LabVIEW system. End of note.

[Responsible: DLR] [Verification: ROD]

LUWEX regolith simulant

1.2.1 Dry regolith simulant

The dry regolith simulant to be used by LUWEX shall be based on a commercial lunar highlands simulant that shall contain >70 Wt.% anorthosite.

Note. Example commercial lunar highlands simulant LHS-1 from Exolith Lab with 74.4Wt.% anorthosite, grain size distribution <math> <0.04 \mu\text{m} - 1000 \mu\text{m}</math>, mean particle size 90 μm . End of note
[Responsible: DLR] [Verification: I]

1.2.2 Ice-regolith simulant physical characteristics

The LUWEX ice-regolith simulant physical characteristics shall be as in Table 1-2.

Table 1-2: LUWEX ice-regolith physical characteristics

Parameter	Value	Remarks
Ice-regolith mass	15 kg	Extraction crucible test load minimal filling level
Water percentage	5-15%	Produced by mixing self-made micro-granular water ice particles with dry lunar regolith analogue. The micro-granular water ice shall have a grain size of $2.4 \pm 0.1 \mu\text{m}$.
Initial temperature	-180°C	
Initial pressure	<math> <10^{-6}</math>mbar	

[Responsible: TUBS, DLR] [Verification: T]

1.2.3 Raw water simulant chemical characteristics

A raw water test simulant containing volatile molecules in concentration characteristic of the LCROSS plume analysis shall mimic volatile liquid composition from the cold trap in the lunar environment. Further, regolith dust simulant shall be added to the test water to verify the WPS filtering technology. The test water shall be added to the raw water prior to injection in the WPS.

Table 1-3: Raw water volatile simulant composition

Volatile molecules in raw water simulant	
Water	H ₂ O
Ammonia	NH ₃
Sulphur dioxide	SO ₂
Carbon dioxide	CO ₂
Methanol	CH ₃ OH

Note 1. The direct introduction of all these volatiles in the TVAC ice-regolith simulant is not recommended for the TVAC chamber due to potential damage to hardware and human safety with respect to some toxic molecules.

Note 2. Volatiles expected to stay in the vapor phase during the cold-trap process shall be neglected (CH₄, H₂, and CO).

Note 3. For human safety reasons, not all of the volatiles measured by LCROSS are added to the raw water simulant.

1.3 Note 4. For LACROSS plume analysis, see "Detection of Water in the LCROSS Ejecta Plume" Anthony Colaprete, et al. Science 330, 463 (2010); DOI: 10.1126/science.1186986. End of notes.

[Responsible: DLR] [Verification: T]

Thermal vacuum chamber (TVAC)

1.3.1 Physical characteristics

The thermal vacuum chamber to be used for extracting water from ice-regolith simulant shall be the L-chamber developed for the Comet Physics Laboratory (CoPhyLab). The L-chamber shall have the following physical characteristics:

- Dimensions 1530 x 700 x 700mm
- Can store prepared ice-regolith samples for > 2 weeks at -170°C
- Maximum pumping rate shall be 37 m³/h allowing theoretically for L-chamber evacuation in minutes
- Pumping rate shall be electronically controlled to reduce damage to samples
- Pump system shall provide continuous ambient pressure of < 10⁻⁶mbar
- Sample cooling system using liquid nitrogen and cold plates to reduce ambient sample temperature to -180°C
- Sample holder platform

[Responsible: TUBS] [Verification: T]

1.3.2 Instrumentation

The TVAC shall provide facilities for the following sensors:

- High-precision scale to measure volatile loss – maximum capacity of 15kg, a resolution of 0:02g over the full range, and a time resolution of 12Hz.
- Mass spectrometer
- Cable interface for external sensors

[Responsible: TUBS] [Verification: I]

1.3.3 Sample crucible physical characteristics

The TVAC shall be able to accommodate a cylindrical sample crucible with following characteristics:

- 30 cm height and diameter of 30 cm.
- Seven heating rods that shall be capable of heating the ice-regolith sample to 0°C.
- Crucible shall be made of stainless steel.
- Heating rods shall be externally controlled by LabVIEW application

[Responsible: DLR, TUBS] [Verification: I]

1.3.4 Sample crucible sensors and temperature monitoring

The sample crucible shall allow for up to 32 temperature sensors and seven heater rods that will be externally monitored/controlled respectively via the LUXEX LabVIEW PC.

[Responsible: DLR, TUBS] [Verification: ROD, I]

1.3.5 TVAC sample loading

The TVAC shall provide an external interface for loading ice-regolith simulant samples into the sample crucible and for extracting used samples.

[Responsible: TUBS] [Verification: I]

1.3.6 Water-volatile cold trap facility

TVAC shall provide a cold trap facility for liquifying extracted water vapour. The facility shall be accommodated within the TVAC vacuum volume.

[Responsible: DLR, TUBS] [Verification: ROD, I]

1.3.7 Raw water storage tank characteristics

The raw water storage tank shall be accommodated outside the TVAC vacuum volume and have the following characteristics:

- Store from 500ml to 2 L of raw water prior to purification by the WPS.

- Water level sensed and monitored by the LUXWEX LabVIEW PC.
- The storage tank shall be isolated as required by manual control valves from the TVAC vacuum environment and external WPS.
- Tank shall be made of stainless steel
- Tank shall be sterilised prior to test sequence to remove bacterial and fungal contamination

Note. It is expected that several liquefaction cycles shall be performed before enough raw water is present in the storage tank for the WPS. End of Note

[Responsible: DLR, TUBS [Verification: ROD, I]

Ice-regolith sample preparation

1.4.1 Micro water-ice generation facility

1.4 Micro-granular water dried ice shall be prepared in an off-line facility that first generates a fog consisting of micrometer-sized water droplets. This fog shall be transferred into liquid nitrogen, which shall cause the water droplets to freeze. Afterwards, the water-ice particle and liquid nitrogen suspension shall be dried in a vacuum chamber (cryo-desiccator) to re-move the liquid nitrogen from the ice.

[Responsible: TUBS [Verification: I]

1.4.2 Micro water-ice physical characteristics

The micro water-ice shall consist of spherical ice particles measuring $2.4 \pm 0.1 \mu\text{m}$.

[Responsible: TUBS [Verification: I]

1.4.3 Ice-regolith sample

Samples prepared in the ice generation facility shall be mixed in a bath of liquid nitrogen to ensure the temperature and to be able to create a homogenous mixture of ice and regolith.

[Responsible: DLR, TUBS [Verification: I]

1.5

Water Purification System (WPS)

1.5.1 WPS Physical Environment

The WPS shall be mounted in a mobile rack system.

[Responsible: TAS] [Verification: I]

1.5.2 WPS dimensions and mass

The WPS (excluding storage units) shall have maximum dimensions 700 x 500 x 400 mm) and mass <25 kg
TBC

[Responsible: TAS] [Verification: RoD, T]

1.5.3 WPS operative environment

The WPS breadboard shall operate in laboratory environment with ambient temperature $22 \pm 5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and relative humidity 30 – 50%.

[Responsible: TAS] [Verification: ROD]

1.5.4 WPS breadboard compatibility with lunar environment

The WPS breadboard shall not be designed to operate in a lunar simulated environment i.e., vacuum, temperatures, dust). It shall operate in a standard laboratory environment.

[Responsible: TAS] [Verification: ROD]

1.5.5 RAMS

The LUWEX system shall fulfil the following **TBD** RAMS requirements.

[Responsible: TAS] [Verification: I TBC]

Water Quality

1.6.1 Raw water quality monitoring control points

The LUWEX design shall allow for monitoring extracted water quality at least at the following points in the processing chain:

1.6

1. Condition monitoring directly after initial extraction process and prior to liquefaction
2. Quality monitoring after liquefaction prior to purification
3. Quality monitoring during purification for each purification step as defined in requirement 2.4.14

Measurements shall include

- Water extraction and liquefaction process characteristics (responsibility of DLR),
- Water quality measurements before purification (e.g., pH, conductivity, TOC) (responsibility of TAS)
- Water quality measurements after purification:
 - pH, TOC (responsibility of TAS and PWR)
 - conductivity, specific contaminants (responsibility of PWR)
 - Laser-Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy (LIBS) data about water composition (responsibility of SW),
- Mass spectroscopy data of vapor release during the water extraction (responsibility of TUBS).

[Responsible: TAS, WUST, SW] [Verification: ROD]

1.6.2 Potable water standard

The LUWEX product water shall comply with NASA potable water standards defined in NASA-STD-3001, Volume 2, Revision B, section 6.3 (TBC) for both microbial and solid particle contamination.

Note1: There are several potential applications of LUWEX product water e.g., electrolysis to O₂/H₂ for propellant. Different standards are assumed. End of note.

Note 2: Tests will be limited to chemical analyses (not microbial)

[Responsible: WUST, SW, TAS] [Verification: T]

1.6.3 Water quality for electrolysis applications

The LUWEX product water shall meet the requirements for electrolysis feed water as in Table 1-5.

Table 1-4: ASTM Standard Specification for high-purity water Type 1 and Type II [ASTM, 2017].

	Type I	Type II
Conductivity in $\mu\text{S}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$ (25°C)	< 0.056	< 1
Resistivity in $\text{M}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}$ (25°C)	> 18	> 1
TOC in $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$	< 50	< 50
Sodium in $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$	< 1	< 5
Silica in $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$	< 3	< 3
Chloride in in $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$	< 1	< 5

Note. In general, fully de-ionized water Type II (less strict requirements) is required but varies across manufacturers and electrolysis systems. Polymer electrolyte membrane (PEM) electrolyzers need a water inlet of Type I with a lower conductivity than Type II [Holst, M. et al., 2021]. Fully deionized water Type I and Type II is defined by the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM).

References:

1. Holst, M. et al., 2021. Cost Forecast for low-temperature Electrolysis – Technology driven bottom-up Prognosis for PEM and alkaline Water Electrolysis Systems, Fraunhofer Institute for Solar Energy Systems ISE.
2. American Society for Testing and Materials, 2017. Standard Specification for Reagent Water, D1193-99e1.

End of note.

[Responsible: TAS] [Verification: T]

Testing

1.7.1 Testing location

- 1.7 All system tests shall be performed in TUBS TVAC facility in Braunschweig, Germany. LUXWEX system monitoring and control shall be performed at the same location using LabVIEW. Overall monitoring and command of the TVAC facility shall be performed by the TUBS team with own control software application. TVAC monitored items data shall be forwarded to LUXWEX LabView PC.

[Responsible: All] [Verification: A, T]

1.7.2 LUXWEX water extraction efficiency

Note. Whichever method is chosen for extracting the water and other volatiles out of the regolith simulant (see requirement 1.1.2), it is necessary to determine the efficiency of the chosen process End of note.

The LUXWEX project shall investigate as part of subsystem testing and modelling the efficiency of the extraction processes.

[Responsible: DLR TUBS] [Verification: A, T]

1.7.3 End-to-end system tests

At the end of the LUXWEX development phase, a complete end-to-end system test shall be performed comprising several parts that each investigate impact of changing initial process parameters on the efficiency of LUXWEX. In particular tests shall be conducted to quantify the impact of varying input parameters such as

- Depth and quantity of regolith
- Ratio of regolith dust and water/volatile ice mix
- Heating cycle and temperature
- Flow rate of water vapor and volatiles to liquefaction chamber

- 1.8 The test campaign shall investigate quality of final water product and efficiency of process in removing volatiles

[Responsible: All] [Verification: T]

Safety

1.8.1 Handling of toxic substances

Handling of toxic substances shall follow standard EU laboratory rules e.g., eye protection when handling toxic liquids.

[Responsible: All] [Verification: I]

1.8.2 Simulant handling

Persons handling exposed regolith simulant shall wear FFP3 masks at all times to avoid inhalation.

[Responsible: All] [Verification: I]

Note. Simulant maybe toxic (see Taylor et al., Potential Toxicology of Lunar Dust, 2006. End of note.

1.8.3 CE Standard

Laboratory equipment shall conform as a minimum to the European Community 'conformité européenne' standard (CE).

[Responsible: All] [Verification: ROD]

2 LUWEX Interface Requirements

Overall Interfaces

The LUWEX overall processing chain and interfaces shall be as shown on Figure 2-1.

Figure 2-1: LUWEX overall process chain and interfaces

TVAC Interfaces

2.2.1 External pump performance

The TVAC shall have access to an external pump system that allows for the internal L-chamber pressure to be reduced to 10^{-6} mbar. The pump system shall comprise a pre-pump prior to a turbo-molecular pump to reduce to final operating pressure.

Note: The use of a pre-pump is necessary to avoid too rapid depressurization when ice-regolith sample present and possible ingestion of material in pump system. End of note

[Responsible: TUBS] [Verification: ROD, I]

2.2.2 TVAC sample cold plate chamber for sample crucible

The TVAC shall provide a hermetically sealed and cooled volume of minimum dimensions 45 x 48 x 63 cm. It shall be possible to depressurize/pressurize this volume.

[Responsible: TUBS] [Verification: ROD, I]

2.2.3 TVAC L-Chamber interface to sample crucible

The TVAC shall provide a mounting platform (donut) for installation of a 30 cm diameter x 30 cm tall cylindrical sample crucible inside its own hermetically sealed cold plate chamber inside the TVAC

[Responsible: TUBS] [Verification: ROD, I]

2.2.4 TVAC L-Chamber sample feeder

The TVAC shall have a pipe feeder system connecting the sample crucible with an external sample fill funnel. The pipe shall have an external valve for hermetically isolating the L-chamber when under vacuum.

[Responsible: TUBS] [Verification: ROD, I]

2.2.5 TVAC sample container monitoring and control

The TVAC shall provide an external harness for monitoring the temperature and pressure of the sample container and for powering the ice-regolith sample heater rod elements.

[Responsible: TUBS] [Verification: ROD, T]

2.2.6 TVAC extracted water-volatile cold trap interface

The TVAC L-chamber shall provide the volume for an internal cold trap to freeze the extracted gaseous water and volatiles. The cold trap shall provide facilities for extracting the frozen products as liquid and storing in a stainless-steel reservoir container external to the TVAC.

[Responsible: DLR, TUBS] [Verification: ROD, T]

Raw Water Reservoir Interfaces

2.3.1 Dimensions

The raw water reservoir shall be capable of storing at least 500 ml of raw water.

2.3.2 Monitoring raw water reservoir

2.3 The volume of the liquid water in the raw water reservoir shall be electronically monitored to assure a minimum 500 ml prior to further processing by the Water Purification System (WPS)

Water Purification Subsystem (WPS) Interfaces

2.4.1 Water phase for WPS processing

2.4 The WPS inlet shall be raw water in liquid phase

[Responsible: TAS] [Verification: ROD]

2.4.2 WPS operating modes

The WPS shall operate in batch mode (reservoir to reservoir- quantity from 0,5 to 1,5 L)

[Responsible: TAS] [Verification: ROD]

2.4.3 WPS raw water composition

The raw water composition for the WPS shall be as in Table 2-1.

Table 2-1: WPS raw water composition

Component	Inlet Water	
	molX/molH ₂ O	mg/L
Methanol	1,50E-06	2,66
Ammonia	9,29E-07	0,879
Sulphur dioxide	2,20E-08	7,83E-02
Particulate	-	5

Note: Composition assumption was made basing on the used simulant composition and on J.B. Holquist, S. Gellenbeck, C.E. Bower, P. Tewes, Experimental proof of concept of a cold trap as a purification step for Lunar water processing, in: 50th International Conference on Environmental Systems, 2021, after water-ice deposition from saturated water vapor (capturing system e.g., cold trap). End of note.

Note2: For human safety reasons and feasibility reasons, not all of the components listed by Holquist are added to the raw water simulant.

[Responsible: DLR] [Verification: T]

2.4.4 WPS raw water processing characteristics

The WPS shall process raw water with minimum flow rate of 10 ml/min ±10%, temperature in the range 4-30 °C and ambient atmospheric pressure.

Note: It is assumed to treat one batch of 1500 ml in max 3 hours to allow one complete experiment to be carried out in one day. End of note

[Responsible: TAS] [Verification: ROD,T]

2.4.5 WPS product water quality

The WPS product water quality shall fulfil purity requirements for electrolysis applications

[Responsible: WUST, SW] [Verification: T]

2.4.6 WPS allowable waste water

The WPS product water to feed ratio shall be >95%

[Responsible: TAS] [Verification: T]

2.4.7 WPS product water physical characteristics

The product water from the WPS shall have a temperature of $25 \pm 10^{\circ}\text{C}$ TBC and pressure 1 bar

[Responsible: TAS] [Verification: T]

2.4.8 WPS allowable consumables

The allowable consumables mass per kg recovered water shall not exceed 1g TBC.

Note: It is assumed that consumables mass shall be <0.1% of product water to support technology convenience. End of note.

[Responsible: TAS] [Verification: ROD]

2.4.9 WPS lifetime performance

The WPS shall be able to treat >150 L (= 100 test runs) TBC raw water during its lifetime without consumables replacement.

Note: It is assumed that the breadboard shall support at least 100 test runs. Sizing the breadboard for larger water quantities would make it too big if compared to a lunar lander demonstrator (surviving only for less than 14 days), providing a non-useful benchmark. End of note.

[Responsible: TAS] [Verification: ROD]

2.4.10 WPS processing parameters monitored

The following process parameters shall be monitored by the WPS for other subsystems via LabVIEW:

- Product water temperature
- Product water pressure
- Product water flow rate
- Product water EC

Note: The sensor data required shall include sensor type, analogue current/voltage, digital, monitoring frequency etc. End of note

[Responsible: TAS] [Verification: T]

2.4.11 WPS power supply

The WPS shall operate with DC power supply with voltages $\leq 28\text{V}$

[Responsible: TAS] [Verification: ROD]

2.4.12 WPS electrical interface standard

Electrical interface type of the WPS toward the system shall be D38999 MIL standard circular connector.

[Responsible: TAS] [Verification: ROD]

2.4.13 WPS fluid interface

The WPS fluid interface connectors shall be of self-locking quick disconnect.

[Responsible: TAS] [Verification: ROD]

2.4.14 WPS sampling ports

The following sampling ports shall be implemented by the WPS:

- Raw water input to WPS
- After particulate filtration
- After reverse osmosis for removal of ammonia and ions
- After activated carbon for removal of methanol and organic
- After ion exchange resins i.e., product water

[Responsible: TAS] [Verification: ROD]

2.4.15 WPS software requirements

The WPS sensors and actuators shall be monitored/controlled via a LabVIEW centralized control system

[Responsible: TAS] [Verification: ROD]

2.5 **Quality and Conditioning Monitoring Interfaces**

2.5.1 Product water quality and condition monitoring

The subsystem design shall include in-line measurements of product water quality parameters and the elemental water analysis using LIBS technology. The essential water quality parameters to be monitored are pH, temperature, pressure, conductivity, turbidity **TBD**, absorbance, and redox potential. In addition to LIBS measurements the monitoring of ions such as Na, Mg and Ca dissolved in extracted water shall be performed using ion-selective electrodes.

[Responsible: WUST, SW] [Verification: ROD]